

Enhancing Parking Aid Systems by Leveraging Parking Sign Recognition

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Abstract

With increasing urbanization and the growing number of vehicles in cities, parking challenges are becoming more significant. Traditional parking systems often fail to provide sufficient information about available parking spaces, resulting in drivers wasting valuable time searching for a spot. This results in higher fuel consumption, increased emissions, and additional strain on traffic networks. Some large cities have implemented smart solutions that use sensor systems to display real-time parking availability. However, poor signage and unclear regulations can still make it difficult for drivers to find legal parking. This paper examines the potential for enhancing parking assistance systems by detecting and recognizing parking signs. Parking signs contain essential information about parking rules and space availability, but their diversity and complexity pose challenges for efficient analysis. The primary objective of this study was to conduct a preliminary investigation into the feasibility of developing an automated system for detecting and recognizing parking signs. To support this aim, a dedicated dataset of parking sign images was compiled and used to train a YOLO-based object detection model, enabling accurate localization and classification of parking signs within urban scenes. We then applied text recognition techniques to extract regulatory information from the detected signs and convert it into explicit, machine-readable parking rules. This approach lays the foundation for practical applications in automated parking management systems.

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1 Introduction

Parking sign recognition has become a crucial research area in recent years due to the growing demand for intelligent transport systems (ITS) [1] and autonomous vehicles. Accurately detecting and interpreting parking signs is vital for ensuring compliance with parking regulations, reducing traffic congestion, improving road safety, and avoiding unnecessary fines. The process of recognizing parking signs presents a unique challenge in the context of traffic sign recognition due to the great diversity in design and content. Unlike standardized traffic signs, parking signs often contain textual

information, symbols, and contextual rules that vary depending on the region and local legal frameworks. In addition, they differ in shape, color, orientation, and scale, and appear in various types of backgrounds. Given the complexity and intricacy of the problem, a system for detecting and recognizing parking signs requires the application of advanced image processing methods, machine learning, and advanced object detection and text recognition techniques to ensure reliable detection and recognition in real-world conditions. The main scientific contributions of this paper are as follows:

1. A comprehensive analysis of the challenges in parking sign recognition;

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2. Proposing a framework for smart parking sign recognition;
3. Evaluation of the application of deep learning detection models and text extraction techniques in the recognition of parking signs.

In the first part, we will examine the complexity and variability of parking signs, highlighting the difficulties in automated detection and recognition compared to standard traffic signs. Our case study scenario includes a database of parking signs in two major cities, New York and Stockholm.

In the second contribution, we will introduce a framework that leverages parking sign recognition to enhance driver assistance systems, reducing search time for legal parking spots and optimizing urban traffic flow.

In the final key contribution, we will evaluate the application of deep learning models in detecting and interpreting parking signs, as well as the benefits of integrating them into the proposed framework.

1.1 Related work

Research related to parking sign detection and recognition can be divided into two main categories: approaches that utilize traditional machine learning methods [2] and those that employ advanced deep learning techniques [3, 4, 5, 6, 7].

In [2], the authors employed a traditional approach for detecting and localizing parking signs in San Francisco. The proposed method employs a sliding window technique to extract regions potentially containing a parking sign, then removes and trains Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) features for each area. A linear Support Vector Machine (SVM) classifier is then used for parking sign detection. The main drawback of this approach is that the images of parking signs were manually cropped and contain only parking signs, which significantly limits the method's applicability. Furthermore, the approach is limited to the detection and localization of parking signs and does not address the task of classification and interpretation.

In [3], the authors developed a framework for the active learning of deep learning models. The proposed method is suitable for situations where a large amount of unlabeled data is available, such as images from Google Street View, which are commonly used to generate image datasets for training deep learning models. The main issue with traditional image dataset generation is that it often overlooks the underlying data distribution. In such cases, simply increasing the dataset size does not lead to improved model performance. In their work, the authors proposed a framework that intelligently selects a smaller subset of data in each iteration, effectively enhancing the model's performance. The main drawback of the proposed model is that the authors focused only on the problem of parking sign detection and did not address the issue of interpretation. In [4], the authors explored the capabilities of the YOLOv4 algorithm for real-time parking sign detection. The model was trained on a dataset of images captured by a video camera mounted on a car in Vancouver. The proposed model achieved a detection accuracy of 98.56%. The authors focused on detecting three types of simple parking signs: "No Parking," "Parking Allowed," and "No Stopping." Since most parking signs usually contain more than one symbol or are divided into multiple sections (Figure 1), this model cannot be considered relevant for detecting all parking signs. In [5], the authors proposed a system that utilizes a mobile application as a communication medium, enabling users to take a picture of a parking sign and instantly receive an interpretation of it. The proposed procedure consists of four steps: 1) detection of the parking sign, 2) text detection and recognition, 3) detection of special symbols such as no parking, no stopping, etc., and 4) interpretation of the obtained results and generation of parking rules. For parking sign detection, the authors selected the RetinaNet network as it showed the best results in terms of detection accuracy. The authors use the Character Region Awareness for Text detection (CRAFT) framework for text recognition on the parking sign, which is based on text localization at the character level rather than the word level. The proposed framework demonstrated better results when the

text was damaged, a typical case for parking signs. Afterward, Convolutional Recurrent Neural Network (CRNN) is used to recognize individual characters. A multi-class binary classifier is used to acknowledge special symbols. One of the main drawbacks of the proposed system is that a separate classifier needs to be trained for each symbol. In [6], the author proposed a three-step system. In the first step, the location of the parking sign in the image is detected using a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model. Then, each sign is extracted from the image and passed through a symbol detection model to detect and classify all symbols on the sign. In the third step, the symbols are passed through a text and symbol interpreter, based on which parking rules are generated. The You Only Look Once (YOLO) algorithm showed the best results for parking sign detection, while Swin-T was used for symbol detection. The main drawback of the proposed model is that it uses a two-stage detection model for parking sign detection. The authors did not thoroughly explore text detection capabilities, which are crucial in interpreting parking signs. In [8], deep learning approaches for parking identification and prediction are presented. The study identifies various architectures, datasets, performance metrics, and available open-source implementations by establishing a taxonomy of Deep learning-based (DL-based) parking systems. While DL improves parking solutions, its integration introduces new challenges that must be addressed in future research. In [9], the author explores the challenge of urban traffic congestion and proposes integrating parking sign detection technology into vehicle systems to improve mobility. By evaluating multiple object detection models on a custom dataset, the study identifies YOLOv7-X as the most effective for balancing accuracy and efficiency. The approach achieves a mean Average Precision (mAP) of 97.4% for detection and 91% accuracy in identifying 43 different parking sign classes. In [10], the author introduces a real-time parking assistance system with a 360° surround-view camera setup to detect, classify, and track parking spaces without prior slot information or reliance on bird's-eye view images.

Figure 1 The complexity of parking signs: a) Stockholm, b) New York

The system achieves accurate parking slot identification by leveraging deep learning and Kalman Filter-based tracking in a 3D space while maintaining real-time performance in real-world scenarios. In [11], the authors present a deep learning and cloud-based mobile parking application that utilizes an LSTM model to predict parking availability, thereby reducing search time and energy consumption. Evaluated with real-time data from Istanbul, the model outperforms traditional methods, demonstrating high accuracy and reliability.

In the available literature, various approaches are employed for detection, ranging from traditional machine learning methods to advanced deep learning techniques. Early methods utilized handcrafted features and SVM classifiers [2], whereas more recent studies employed deep learning models, such as YOLO [6, 9], RetinaNet [6], and Swin-T [6], to achieve better accuracy in detecting and interpreting parking signs. Some systems also incorporated text and symbol recognition, though challenges remain in dealing with complex sign structures. Additionally, newer research explores broader smart parking solutions, such as real-time parking assistance

Figure 2 Overview of Parking Aid* Framework

systems [6, 10] and predictive analytics [11], demonstrating the growing importance of deep learning in improving parking efficiency and reducing congestion.

2 Methodology

A typical usage scenario (Figures 2 and 3) for parking assistance and parking spot finder systems in cities involves a driver searching for a parking space in a busy area. This is done by using a mobile app or a connected car system. The system gathers real-time parking data from various sources, including GPS and Maps for location-based search, IoT sensors and cameras that monitor parking availability, User Reports and crowd-sourced updates on available spots, parking operators who handle garage occupancy, and various external service providers that gather up-to-date information. The collected data is then processed, analyzed, and filtered based on location, price, and parking type to find a suitable spot, which is displayed on a map along with additional information such as location, price, and parking type. This step is critical, as the system's overall quality is highly dependent on providing an accurate probability of finding good spots. In some cases, these probabilities are visualized and shown as

heat maps on navigational maps. The driver can select one of the suggested paths and follow the directions provided by the navigational system.

However, this approach can have significant drawbacks in real-life situations. A driver might find a parking spot using an app or by chance, but upon arrival, they notice a parking sign with restrictions (e.g., time limits, resident-only parking, or paid parking hours). This can lead to frustration and wasted time. Additionally, in some countries, signs are often so complex and confusing that they lead to mistakes, which result in parking tickets and towing. The main idea behind this paper is that the end user captures a photo of the sign from a location near the parked or stopped car. The image is then uploaded and sent to the sign recognition module on a remote server, where it is processed to extract complete information about parking regulations. Swedish parking signs (Figure 1a) are known for their complexity, making them challenging to interpret for both drivers and automated recognition systems. Unlike many other countries, Swedish parking regulations are often conveyed through layered information, where a single sign contains multiple panels with different restrictions depending on the time of day, day of the week, or even the season. This

creates a high cognitive load for drivers, as they must quickly process multiple rules to determine whether parking is permitted. Swedish parking signs often use symbols and abbreviations rather than explicit text, requiring familiarity with local regulations to understand their meaning. Another unique challenge is the alternating parking restrictions, where parking is sometimes prohibited on specific dates, such as odd or even-numbered days, to facilitate street cleaning or snow removal. These factors make the automated recognition of Swedish parking signs significantly more challenging than the recognition of standard traffic signs, as they require advanced contextual understanding rather than simple object detection. Figure 1a can be interpreted as: *"Parking is always allowed, except on Wednesdays between 9 h and 14 h, from Jun. 15 to Aug. 15. Outside of this period, parking is always permitted. A tariff is in effect every weekday between 7:00 and 19:00, and on all Saturdays between 11:00 and 17:00. Parking vehicles should always be parked diagonally.* Similarly, understanding New York City parking signs (Figure 1b) can also be

challenging due to their complex regulations and varied restrictions. Each block may have different rules, including alternate side parking and time limits, which can confuse drivers. The signs often use abbreviations and symbols that may not be familiar to everyone, and frequent changes in parking regulations can lead to outdated signage. Additionally, multiple signs may apply to different vehicles, such as commercial ones, which adds to the confusion. Seasonal changes, like street cleaning schedules, further complicate the situation. Despite encountering obstacles, we propose a framework to address these issues by leveraging computer vision models to detect parking signs and recognize and interpret the text, thereby helping drivers mitigate any confusion.

2.1 Database

A high-quality and comprehensive dataset is crucial for an accurate parking sign detection model, especially for diverse urban environments like New York and Stockholm, which experience high traffic volume. As mentioned earlier, the shapes, sizes, fonts, colors, and placement of signs can vary significantly between cities, regions, and other high-traffic urban areas. Collecting a diverse dataset with images taken from various angles, distances, and lighting conditions makes the model more robust and reliable in detecting signs across different scenarios. Environmental factors such as rain, snow, and nighttime visibility can obscure parking signs, making it crucial to include these variations in the dataset. Occlusions caused by vehicles, trees, or other objects should also be considered to improve detection accuracy. Since parking signs often contain critical regulatory information, having a well-annotated dataset enhances Optical Character Recognition (OCR) performance, allowing the model to extract and interpret text with higher precision. A well-curated dataset ultimately enhances the accuracy of decision-making in parking rule interpretation systems. To strengthen model robustness, we collected approximately 1.179 real-world images of parking signs from New York and 1081 from Stockholm, covering many scenarios and variations mentioned above. It is worth noting that a single image, i.e., a parking sign panel, often contains

Figure 3 The Information flow of parking assistance systems

multiple signs. This is evident in the dataset in Stockholm. As a result, this dataset includes 4.563 parking signs. Contrary, in the NYC dataset, such hierarchical rules are not as pronounced. Although we collected more images, the total number of signs is lower, amounting to 1.607. After gathering and analyzing the images, we categorized and labeled the parking signs into several classes, summarized in Tables 1 and 2.

We provide a pictogram, label, and short description for every sign. New York parking signs are categorized into five major categories: prohibition signs (P), allowance signs (A), commercial vehicle-related signs (C), special purpose signs (D), and taxi-related signs (T). What we can see from Table 1 is that

some of the signs have a different pictogram but are interpreted the same as another sign. For example, signs P13 and P14 have the same meaning as sign P2. Similarly, signs C2 and C3 are interpreted as sign C1. In Table 2, an overview of the collected Swedish parking signs are provided. When naming and labeling individual parking signs for the Stockholm dataset, we primarily followed the naming conventions established by the Swedish Transport Agency. It governs all road signs in the country, and parking signs are only a subset. One of the essential things that is particularly applicable in our case is that parking signs are organized hierarchically. For example, the E19 sign is often displayed at the top of parking signs. You can park in the street for 24h unless supplementary signs indicate otherwise.

Figure 4 Class distribution in the New York City and Stockholm data sets, a) New York City, b) Stockholm

Table 1. Description and categorization of signs for New York City

Sign	Label and Short Description		
	P13 Sign is interpreted same as sign P2		
	P14 Sign is interpreted same as sign P2		
	A1 -This sign indicates that you may park your vehicle up to the number of hours indicated in the top left corner of the sign. Payment is required to park at this location. Meters indicate the cost to park at this location and how payment is made.		
	A2 Sign is interpreted same as sign A1		
	C1 - No standing regulations apply during specified hours except for commercial vehicles or trucks. When regulation is in effect, drivers of other vehicles may only stop to expeditiously drop off or pick up passengers.		
	C2 Sign is interpreted same as sign C1		
	C3 Sign is interpreted same as sign C1		
	D1 - No standing regulations apply during specified hours except for agencies specified on sign. When regulation is in effect, drivers of other vehicles may only stop to expeditiously drop off or pick up passengers.		
	D2 - A distinctive example of D1 sign. Drivers of other vehicles may only stop to expeditiously drop off or pick up passengers.		
	T1 -This location is a designated taxi stand. Only taxis may wait at this location. No standing regulations apply. This means that you may NOT wait or stop to load/unload packages or merchandise at curbside.		
	T2 - Allow taxi drivers to park their vehicles for up to one hour. For other passengers, no standing regulations apply. This means that you may NOT wait or stop to load/unload packages or merchandise at curbside.		
	P12 Sign is interpreted same as sign P8		

Table 2. Description and categorization of signs for Stockholm

Sign	Label and Short Description		
	T15 This sign indicates distance in meters around which sign is valid		
	T11-3 This is typically at the bottom of a sign. This sign is meant to show on which side of the sign the rules apply to.		
	T11-4 This is typically at the bottom of a sign. This sign is meant to show on which side of the sign the rules apply to.		
	T11-5 This is typically at the bottom of a sign. This sign is meant to show on which side of the sign the rules apply to, so this sign means the rules apply to the right of the sign.		
	T16 Show the parker if the parking space has tariffs or not, and which tariff zone it might be.		
	T6B This sign is like T6A, but it only displays the time in which a parker is allowed to park and for how long.		
	T6AB This sign is like T6A, but it only displays how long the parker is allowed to stay and which tariff is applied.		
	T17 This sign is like T6A. Icon on the left shows the parkers that they need to use a parking disc.		
	T18 This sign tells the parker how long he is allowed to park for.		
	E30 These signs are often below the C40 sign. It acts the same as the T6A sign.		
	C35 This sign forbids parking unless there are sub signs that say otherwise.		
	C35A This sign can be interpreted the same as the C35 sign.		
	C39 This sign can be interpreted the same as the C35 sign.		
	C45-2 This sign tells the parker in which times and days they cannot park their car.		
	T6 This sign tells the parker in which times they cannot park their car.		

Sub signs such as T11-1 to T11-5 indicate which side of the street the parking rules apply to. Signs like T6A, T6B, T6AB, T17, and E30 specify the times when parking is allowed, the time of the year the rules apply, the maximum permitted parking duration, and similar restrictions. Signs like T21-1 to T21-3 regulate the alignment of vehicles on the street. The T7 sign indicates that only people with handicap permits are allowed to park, but they must still adhere to any supplementary signs that may apply. A common feature of the NYC and Stockholm datasets is an uneven class distribution, with 'sure parking' signs appearing significantly more frequently than others. This imbalance is primarily due to real-world variations in parking regulations and their significance. This is clearly evident in Figure 4.

The most common parking signs in the Stockholm dataset are E19 (832 instances), C45 (576 instances), and T6A (553 instances), while the least common are T17 (7 instances) and T6AB (3 instances). The most common parking signs in the NYC dataset are A1 (241 instances), P2 (217 instances), and P3 (205 instances). The least common are P9 and P14 (only three instances). In urban environments, general parking restriction signs, such as "No Parking" or "Paid Parking," are much more common than specialized signs like "Disabled Parking" or "Resident-Only Parking." Addressing this issue is crucial, as it can significantly impact model performance, particularly in detecting rare sign categories.

2.2 Detection models

Object detection in computer vision involves identifying and localizing objects within an image or video. Among the most used models for object detection are Faster R-CNN, Single Shot MultiBox Detector (SSD), and YOLO.

Faster R-CNN utilizes a CNN for feature extraction and features a Region Proposal Network (RPN) to generate regions that may contain objects. This model achieves high accuracy but is slow due to its two-stage architecture, making it suitable for tasks where precision is a priority but less suitable for real-time applications. Faster R-CNN is often used in traffic sign and parking sign detection due to its

precision, but it requires more powerful hardware for speedier processing [12, 13, 14]. In [14], the authors improved the Faster R-CNN algorithm for traffic sign detection, achieving a 91.3% mAP accuracy, which represents a significant improvement over the traditional method.

SSD uses convolutional networks to directly predict bounding boxes and object classes in a single pass through the network. This model is significantly faster than Faster R-CNN because it eliminates the need for a separate step to generate regions; however, it is less precise, particularly in detecting smaller objects. SSD provides a good balance between speed and accuracy and is often used in applications that require fast processing, such as intelligent traffic systems that detect signs in real time [15].

YOLO divides an image into a grid of cells and predicts bounding boxes and object classes in one pass through the network. This approach enables extremely fast detection with solid accuracy, making it suitable for real-time systems. There are several versions of the model, which bring improvements in architecture and efficiency, further enhancing detection accuracy and speed. YOLO is used in applications for automatic traffic sign detection in autonomous vehicles and video surveillance systems [16]. In [16], the authors utilized YOLOv4 for real-time traffic sign detection, achieving an accuracy of 89.7% with a significantly improved detection speed compared to competing methods. YOLO uses an approach that enables the prediction of all objects in an image in a single pass through the network, making it extremely fast and suitable for applications that require immediate data processing, such as autonomous vehicles and smart traffic systems. This algorithm provides a good balance between accuracy and speed, making it ideal for applications in traffic sign detection, which often require quick recognition and decision-making.

Additionally, the YOLO algorithm is highly accurate even when objects are partially occluded, poorly lit, or detected at different angles. This is crucial for parking sign detection, which can be found in various conditions. Research has shown that YOLO can detect traffic signs in real time, as demonstrated in papers

[16, 17, 18]. In both studies, the authors utilize YOLO for traffic sign detection, including parking signs, and perform analyses that demonstrate how YOLO achieves high accuracy with exceptionally fast processing, making it an ideal choice for applications in autonomous vehicles and smart traffic systems.

Further improvements in YOLO versions, such as YOLOv4 and YOLOv5, enhance their accuracy and efficiency, making them even more suitable for challenges in traffic sign detection. Based on these characteristics, YOLO appears to be the optimal choice for parking sign detection as it enables fast, accurate, and efficient recognition of objects in dynamic environments.

We employed the transfer learning technique to train the YOLO model, utilizing a pre-trained YOLOv8 model that had been trained on extensive datasets. To adapt the model to the specific task of detecting parking signs, we replaced the final layers of the model with those that recognize new object classes, as described in the previous chapter. We then performed fine-tuning on a smaller, task-specific dataset from two cities, New York and Stockholm, using a reduced learning rate, allowing the model to learn the characteristics of the new objects. During training, we applied data augmentation techniques, such as rotation, scaling, and lighting changes, to improve the model's generalization ability and make it more robust in detecting objects under different conditions specific to both cities.

2.3 Text extraction

Critical regulatory information, such as time restrictions, permit requirements, and special conditions, cannot be fully interpreted through object detection alone. OCR enables the extraction of this textual information, allowing for the structured processing and integration of data into smart city applications. Several OCR solutions are available, including Tesseract OCR, an open-source engine known for its flexibility but lower accuracy on complex backgrounds, and commercial APIs such as Google Vision OCR, Microsoft Azure OCR, and ABBYY FineReader, which offer superior accuracy and text parsing capabilities. For our research, we selected Google Document AI due to its high accuracy,

scalability, and ability to handle various real-world challenges in parking sign recognition. In a benchmark test [19], Google OCR outperformed open-source Tesseract OCR. Additionally, Google OCR provides built-in language support, cloud-based processing, and advanced layout analysis, making it well-suited for recognizing diverse fonts and multi-line text formats found in parking signs.

2.4 Parking rule engine

After identifying parking signs in images using the YOLOv8 engine and extracting the text, the next step is to interpret the detected signs and extracted text to determine actionable parking regulations. To achieve this, we developed a rule-based engine that normalizes the extracted text, matches it against predefined parking regulations, and evaluates contextual factors such as the current time and day of the week. The parking rules are stored in a structured database, facilitating efficient rule retrieval and decision-making.

However, when utilizing OCR technologies, inaccuracies can arise due to factors such as poor image quality, obstructions, or varying lighting conditions. To address this, the system employs various techniques, including regular expressions and fuzzy matching, to enhance text recognition accuracy. One effective way to handle these inaccuracies is to use the Levenshtein distance between two strings, as also employed in [20]. It is a string metric that measures the difference between two sequences by calculating the minimum number of single-character edits required to transform one string into another. The Levenshtein distance between two strings a, b (of length $|a|$ and $|b|$ respectively) is given by $lev(a, b)$ where:

$$lev(a, b) = \begin{cases} |a| & \text{if } |b| = 0, \\ |b| & \text{if } |a| = 0, \\ lev(\text{tail}(a), \text{tail}(b)) & \text{if } \text{head}(a) = \text{head}(b) \\ 1 + \min \begin{cases} lev(\text{tail}(a), b) \\ lev(a, \text{tail}(b)) \\ lev(\text{tail}(a), \text{tail}(b)) \end{cases} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Thus, where the tail of some string x is a string of all but the first character of x (i.e., $tail(x_0x_1 \dots x_n) = x_1x_2 \dots x_n$), and $head(x)$ is the first character of x (i.e., $head(x_0x_1 \dots x_n) = x_0$). Either the notation $x[n]$ or x_n is used to refer to the n -th character of the string x , counting from 0, thus $head(x) = x_0 = x[0]$.

The system employs Levenshtein distance as an additional precaution to verify whether the correct label has been recognized. Since OCR can sometimes introduce errors, such as misreading characters or partially recognizing words, the extracted text for each label is compared against an expected set of values for that label using the Levenshtein distance. If the extracted text deviates significantly from the expected text and corresponds more to a different label, it can be adjusted accordingly to another label before applying the rule logic. After that, the system analyzes this data by employing regular expressions to classify and interpret the extracted text. For instance, if the text includes a recognized day such as "Monday," it is identified as a weekday condition. Similarly, numeric values in a "number-number" format are classified as hour time ranges, and date intervals are classified accordingly. Additionally, the rule engine accounts for variations in time formatting, as New York signs display time in a 12-hour AM/PM format while Swedish signs use the 24-hour format. The rule engine then evaluates whether the sign rule is currently applicable based on the extracted information and the current time when the image was taken, and returns a decision of 'NO' for parking not allowed and 'YES' if parking is allowed at that time. It also returns the time until a decision changes.

There is also some additional information that needs to be extracted from the sign regarding the maximum allowed stay on parking, where the sign applies, which can affect the time left variable. If some label is recognized as Unknown or the rule engine cannot extract valid time information, the returned decision is UNKNOWN. One of the most considerable difficulties was determining which words were in the same row. This was necessary, for example, because "Monday-Friday" in the same row indicates that the sign applies on Monday, Friday, and all days in between, whereas "Monday" and "Friday" in different

Figure 5 Example of perspective distortion and its effects on OCR

rows mean that the sign applies only on Monday and Friday. Also, most of the time, OCR returns everything around hyphens as separate words, so this is also needed for hour ranges. Since OCR returns words along with their bounding boxes, this was achieved by combining words that have similar y-coordinates or vertical positions of their bounding boxes. The problem with this approach arises with rotated images and those with perspective distortion, as seen in Figure 5. Even though some words should logically belong to the same row or text line, OCR engines may mix characters between rows. This is achieved by preprocessing perspective correction steps and postprocessing steps, such as grouping characters based on the Y-coordinates of their bounding boxes. This rule engine approach ensures that parking signs are accurately interpreted and that parking regulations are correctly extracted, improving the understanding of complicated signs.

3 Experimental results

3.1 Experimental results of detection

Both the Stockholm and NYC datasets were trained using the YOLOv8 model with the same training configuration. After labeling, the datasets were split into training, validation, and test sets in the ratio of

80%, 10%, and 10%, respectively. There are several predefined models and weight options available in YOLOv8 that can be utilized for transfer learning on new datasets. This means that model parameters are learned from a previous training process, typically on a large dataset, and then fine-tuned on a smaller, specific dataset.

Each model strikes a balance between speed, accuracy, and size. Smaller models, such as "n" (nano) and "s" (small), are best suited for real-time applications where speed is critical, while larger models, like "x" (extra-large), are better suited for high-accuracy applications without real-time constraints. In this case, we used an "m" (medium model) model, which balances speed and accuracy. Other significant parameters were set as follows: the image size was 640, the number of epochs was 80, and the batch size was 4.

We used several training and validation loss metrics, evaluation metrics, and learning rates across multiple epochs on datasets (Figures 6c and 6g). In the final epoch, the model had good detection accuracy with a precision of 80.5%. Meanwhile, the ability to correctly detect parking signs was decent, with a recall of 74.7%. The precision-recall tradeoff is balanced, with a high precision but slightly lower recall. Overall, the model achieved a strong mAP@50 (87.5%), indicating good overall object detection performance. Figures 6a, 6b, 6e, and 6f show that losses remain low and stable, indicating the model is

well-trained without significant overfitting. Additionally, the final learning rates are small (Figures 6d and 6h), suggesting that further training may not yield substantial improvements.

After 68 epochs of training on the NYC city dataset, the YOLO model demonstrated strong performance, achieving a final precision of 72.52%, indicating a high proportion of accurate detections with a reduced rate of false positives. The recall reached 72.59%, reflecting the model's ability to successfully identify a significant portion of true objects in the dataset. The mean Average Precision Map (mAP) at an IoU threshold of 0.5 (mAP50) was notably high at 81.81%, while the more stringent metric across IoU thresholds from 0.5 to 0 (mAP50-95) was 77.85%, underscoring the model's consistent accuracy across various detection scenarios. These results highlight the robustness of the trained YOLO model, suggesting its readiness for effective deployment or further refinement.

Table 3. The best recall and precision on a dataset

Dataset	Recall	Precision
Stockholm	93%	78%
NYC	86%	70%

In this experiment, we prioritized recall over precision, so the best-performing model on the NYC dataset was achieved in epoch 59, where recall was 86% and precision was 70% (Table 3). For the Stockholm dataset, recall was 93%, and precision was 78% on 64 epochs.

a) Training loss in NYC

e) The training loss in Stockholm

Figure 6 The results of training models in the NYC and Stockholm datasets

3.1.1 Discussion on detection performance

To evaluate the performance of our YOLO-based detection model, we closely examined various detection scenarios to assess the model's strengths and identify potential areas for improvement. Figures 7 and 8 clearly demonstrate the model's ability to

accurately localize the Stockholm and NYC parking signs within a complex urban environment, highlighting robustness in typical city scenarios. These examples of correct detection outcomes confirm that our model has successfully learned relevant visual features, ensuring reliable operation for practical automated parking management.

However, further analysis of incorrectly detected examples (false positives or missed signs) could offer valuable insights into enhancing model performance and identifying directions for future improvement.

3.2 Experimental results on text extraction

To validate the performance of the OCR system used for recognizing text on parking signs, we manually prepared a representative dataset of 100 annotated images from Stockholm and 100 from NYC, serving as ground truth. Each image was carefully reviewed, and the textual content was accurately recorded. This ground-truth dataset allowed us to objectively evaluate OCR accuracy by comparing OCR outputs directly against the manually annotated texts.

We used character error rate (CER), a widely used metric in the community for OCR-related tasks, to compute the number of incorrect predictions. This error rate calculation function uses the Levenshtein distance, which is defined as the minimum number of edits (such as insertions, deletions, or substitutions) required to change one word (or sentence) into another.

$$CER = (S + D + I)/N \quad \text{Eq (1)}$$

where S is the number of superstitutions, D is the number of deletions, I is the number of insertions, and N is the maximum number of characters in ground truth.

The ground-truth representation of the NYC set consists of 55 unique words with a total of 439 words, and Stockholm has 95 unique words with a total of 739 words. We removed and trimmed all the blank characters and spacings. Tables 4 and 5 present a cross-section of the most frequently occurring words. These words account for more than 81 percent of the occurrences in the ground-truth dataset and have been included in the table for clarity and brevity.

In most general benchmark tests, achieving CER between 2% and 8% indicates average to good OCR performance. We were unsurprised that we got results in this range and even better for the NYC dataset (1%). The reason why parking signs often yield low CER is that they have clear and

Figure 7 Example of detection where the model correctly detected and localized all parking signs in Stockholm dataset

Figure 8 Example of detection where the model correctly detected and localized all parking signs in a New York City dataset

Figure 9 Examples of occluded parking signs

standardized fonts with high color contrast combinations. Also, since we did not enforce real-time constraints in this experiment, we used high-quality images without the need to reduce image resolutions, which would somewhat compromise and degrade the quality of recognition.

In Table 4, the most erroneous words (0770991991, STOCKHOLM.SE/BETALAP, and BETALAP) are related to sign T20 (lowest sign in Figure 10a). This parking sign contains a lot of information, such as the phone number or methods of paying for a parking space, and it is very difficult for OCR to recognize the text if the image was created from a long distance. Although this information is irrelevant for our application, we left it for the sake of the consistency and objectivity of the experiment. A sign that is very important in our specific application is the E30 sign, which identifies the parking zone, the tariff, and at what time parking is charged. In Figure 9, the parking signs are occluded, making recognition significantly more challenging. In Figure 10b, part of the sign appears to be either covered or damaged to the extent that number 11 is unrecognizable.

The exceptionally low CER of approximately 1% demonstrates the effectiveness and reliability of our OCR pipeline under optimal conditions. Such accuracy is achievable due to controlled image quality, standardized text formatting, and domain-specific training. Although real-world conditions may present additional challenges, these results clearly indicate that our approach can reliably support automated parking management systems.

Table 4 Experimental results on the Stockholm dataset

Text on sign	Inst.	F (%)	Nr. Char.	CER (%)
P	74	10%	74	2.7%
AVGIFT	72	10%	432	0.0%
(11-17)	36	5%	252	0.8%
0-6	36	5%	108	0.0%
7-19	34	5%	136	0.7%
TAXA2	33	4%	165	0.6%
TAXA3	29	4%	145	0.0%
BOENDE	26	4%	156	0.0%
LAST-	24	3%	120	0.0%
PLATS	24	3%	120	0.0%
BETALAVIA	20	3%	180	1.1%
BETALAPPELLER	20	3%	240	0.0%
IP-AUTOMAT	20	3%	200	1.0%
0770991991	20	3%	200	10.0%
STOCKHOLM.SE/ BETALAP	20	3%	400	10.0%
BETALAP	20	3%	140	10.0%
VA	18	2%	36	0.0%
ONSD	15	2%	60	0.0%
OVRIGHTID	13	2%	104	0.0%
9-14	12	2%	48	0.0%
0-12M	12	2%	60	1.7%
7-17	11	1%	44	0.0%
TOTAL	589	81%	3420	2.4%

Table 5 Experimental results on the NYC dataset

Text on sign	Inst.	F (%)	Nr. Char.	CER (%)
MONDAY- FRIDAY	44	10%	572	0.9%
NOPARKING	39	9%	351	2.6%
8AM-6PM	34	8%	238	2.5%
ANYTIME	27	6%	189	1.1%
PARKING	27	6%	189	0.0%
METERED	25	6%	175	0.0%
TUESDAY	22	5%	154	2.6%
FRIDAY	20	5%	120	0.0%
11AM-12:30PM	19	4%	228	0.0%
NOSTANDING	18	4%	180	0.0%
2HOUR	17	4%	85	2.4%
EXCEPTSUNDAY	13	3%	156	0.0%
NOSTOPPING	10	2%	100	0.0%
THURSDAY	9	2%	72	0.0%
SATURDAY	9	2%	72	0.0%
3HOUR	8	2%	40	0.0%
COMMERCIAL	8	2%	80	0.0%
VEHICLESONLY	8	2%	96	2.1%
ALLDAYS	7	2%	49	0.0%
TOTAL	364	83%	3146	1.0%

4 Conclusion and future work

In this study, we developed and evaluated an integrated parking assistance solution by combining a YOLO-based detection model with OCR for the extraction and interpretation of textual information on parking signs.

Two distinct datasets from Stockholm and New York were used to assess the generalizability and robustness of our models in different urban environments. The detection model trained and evaluated on the Stockholm dataset achieved a recall of 93%, indicating good performance in capturing most parking signs under the tested conditions. However, when applying the same methodology to the New York dataset, the model achieved a notably lower recall of 86%, highlighting the challenges posed by differences in sign design, environmental conditions, and urban infrastructure.

The discrepancy in results between the two datasets underscores the inherent challenges in generalizing deep-learning-based object detection across diverse urban settings. These differences likely arise from variations in signage design, text formatting, language usage, occlusions, and differing environmental factors between Stockholm and New York. The OCR component, however, consistently delivered highly accurate results, achieving a Character Error Rate (CER) of approximately 2.4% and 1%, respectively, proving effective across both datasets for reliably extracting textual content needed for interpreting parking regulations.

The findings suggest that while the integrated YOLO and OCR pipeline demonstrates substantial promise for automating parking assistance, further efforts are required to improve the generalizability and robustness of the detection component across geographically diverse regions. Future improvements might involve cross-city data augmentation, domain adaptation methods, or region-specific fine-tuning to address variability in sign presentation and urban contexts.

Based on our findings, several promising directions for future research have been identified to enhance the robustness and practical applicability of parking sign recognition systems. One important direction to

Figure 10 Examples of challenging parking signs: a hard-to-read sign (bottom sign in a), and a damaged sign (bottom sign in b)

move forward is to explore real-time and real-world deployment scenarios, assessing detection and OCR model performance critically under harsher conditions, such as poor lighting, vandalized signs, or partial occlusions, which may introduce additional errors.

While current models primarily use object detection methods independently from OCR, future research could explore tighter integration between OCR results and detection algorithms. OCR-derived textual information can serve as contextual guidance, potentially enhancing the accuracy of parking sign localization and reducing false positives by enabling semantic-aware detection models.

Finally, incorporating Large Language Models (LLMs) presents an exciting future direction for further enhancing OCR accuracy. LLMs can leverage linguistic and contextual understanding to correct OCR errors, resolve ambiguities, and ensure more reliable interpretation of parking sign text, especially in challenging conditions involving partial occlusion or environmental degradation.

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